

A Theorem on the Binomial Coefficients of Combinatorial Geometric Series and Some Solutions on Partitions of the Binomial Coefficients

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Abstract: This paper presents a theorem on the binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series and its solutions for the binomial expression under the partitions of the binomial coefficients. The coefficient for each term in combinatorial geometric series refers to a binomial coefficient. These ideas can enable the scientific researchers to solve the real life problems.

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1. Introduction

When the author of this article was trying to develop the multiple summations of geometric series, a new idea was stimulated his mind to create a combinatorial geometric series [1-11]. The combinatorial geometric series is a geometric series whose coefficient of each term of the geometric series denotes the binomial coefficient V_n^r . In this article, binomial identities and multinomial theorem is provided using the binomial coefficients for combinatorial geometric series.

2. Combinatorial Geometric Series

The combinatorial geometric series [1-11] is derived from the multiple summations of geometric series. The coefficient of each term in the combinatorial refers to the binomial coefficient V_n^r .

$$\sum_{i_1=0}^n \sum_{i_2=i_1}^n \sum_{i_3=i_2}^n \cdots \sum_{i_r=i_{r-1}}^n x^{i_r} = \sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i \quad \& \quad V_n^r = \frac{(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)\cdots(n+r-1)(n+r)}{r!},$$

where $n \geq 0, r \geq 1$ and $n, r \in N = \{0, 1, 2, 3, \dots\}$.

Here, $\sum_{i=0}^n V_i^r x^i$ refers to the combinatorial geometric series and

V_n^r is the binomial coefficient for combinatorial geometric series.

Theorem 2. 1: $1 + V_1^n + V_2^n + V_3^n + \cdots + V_n^n = V_{n+1}^n, (n \geq 1 \& n \in N)$.

Proof. This new theorem is constituted on the binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series step by step.

Step 1: $1 + V_1^1 = V_2^1 \Rightarrow 1 + 2 = 3$.

Step 2: $1 + V_1^2 + V_2^2 = V_3^2 \Rightarrow 1 + 3 + 6 = 10$.

Step 3: $1 + V_1^3 + V_2^3 + V_3^3 = V_4^3 \Rightarrow 1 + 3 + 10 + 35 = 35.$

Step 4: $1 + V_1^4 + V_2^4 + V_3^4 + V_4^4 = V_5^4 \Rightarrow 1 + 5 + 15 + 35 + 70 = 126.$

Step 5: $1 + V_1^5 + V_2^5 + V_3^5 + V_4^5 + V_5^5 = V_6^5 \Rightarrow 1 + 6 + 21 + 56 + 126 + 252 = 462.$

If we continue the expressions up to “**Step n**”, we get as follows:

Step n: $1 + V_1^n + V_2^n + V_3^n + V_4^n + \dots + V_{n-1}^n + V_n^n = V_{n+1}^n.$

3. Partition of Binomial Coefficient

We can partition a binomial coefficient into sum of two parts.

Theorem 3. 1: $V_n^r = V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1}, (n, r \geq 1 \ \& \ n, r \in N).$

Proof. Let us apply Theorem 2.1 in the partition of a binomial coefficient.

$$V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1} = \frac{(n+r-1)!}{n!(r-1)!} + \frac{(r+n-1)!}{r!(n-1)!}, \quad \text{where } (n+r-1) = (r+n-1).$$

So, $V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1} = (n+r-1)! \left(\frac{1}{n!(r-1)!} + \frac{1}{r!(n-1)!} \right).$

By simplifying this expression, we get

$$V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1} = (n+r-1)! \left(\frac{r}{n!r!!} + \frac{n}{r!n!} \right) = \frac{(n+r-1)!(r+n)}{n!r!} = \frac{(n+r)!}{n!r!} = V_n^r.$$

Hence, theorem is proved.

The successive partitions [6, 7] applied to a binomial coefficient (root) V_n^r are given below:

$$V_n^r = V_n^{r-1} + V_r^{n-1}.$$

$$V_n^r = (V_n^{r-2} + V_{r-1}^{n-1}) + (V_r^{n-2} + V_{n-1}^{r-1}).$$

$$V_n^r = (V_n^{r-3} + V_{r-2}^{n-1}) + (V_{r-1}^{n-2} + V_{n-1}^{r-2}) + (V_r^{n-3} + V_{n-2}^{r-1}) + (V_{n-1}^{r-2} + V_{r-1}^{n-2}).$$

Similarly, we can partition each item into sum of two parts again and again.

The final binomial coefficient (leaf) under the successive partitions of V_n^r (root) is given below:

$$V_{r-k}^{n-n} \text{ or } V_{n-k}^{r-r}, (n-k \geq 1 \ \& \ r-k \geq 1).$$

The binomial coefficients between root and leaves are named as predecessors and successors.

Also, we can show these root, predecessors, successors, and leaves in a tree diagram.

Let us do some math exercises with partitions on the Theorem 2.1.

Simplify the following problems using partition method. Note that the binomial coefficient V_n^n is a root and the a binomial coefficient $V_k^0, (k \geq 1 \ \& \ k \in N)$ is a leaf in partitions of V_n^n and $V_n^n = 2V_n^{n-1}.$

(i). $1 + V_1^1 = V_2^1$ (ii). $1 + V_1^2 + V_2^2 = V_3^2$ (iii). $1 + V_1^3 + V_2^3 + V_3^3 = V_4^3$

Solution for (i):

(i). $1 + V_1^1 = V_2^1$; Here $V_1^1 = 2V_1^0 = 2$, ($\because V_k^0 = 1$ for $k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$).
 $1 + V_1^1 = 1 + 2 = 3 = V_2^1$.

Solution for (ii):

$1 + V_1^2 + V_2^2 = 1 + V_1^2 + 2V_2^1 = 1 + 3V_2^1 = 1 + 3(V_2^0 + V_1^1) = 1 + 3 + 3(2V_1^0) = 1 + 3 + 6$.
 $\therefore 1 + V_1^2 + V_2^2 = V_3^2 = 10$. (Here, $V_r^n = V_n^r$; $n, r \geq 1$ & $n, r \in N$).

Solution for (iii):

$1 + V_1^3 + V_2^3 + V_3^3 = 1 + V_1^3 + V_2^3 + 2V_3^2 = 1 + V_1^3 + 3V_3^2 = 1 + V_1^3 + 3(V_3^1 + V_2^2)$
 $= 1 + 4V_3^1 + 3V_2^2 = 1 + 4(V_3^0 + V_2^1) + 3(2V_2^1) = 1 + 4 + 10V_2^1$
 $= 1 + 4 + 10(V_2^0 + V_1^1) = 1 + 4 + 10 + 10(2V_1^0) = 1 + 4 + 10 + 20$.
 $\therefore 1 + V_1^3 + V_2^3 + V_3^3 = 1 + 4 + 10 + 20 = 35 = V_4^3$.

4. Conclusion

In this article, a theorem was built on the binomial coefficients of combinatorial geometric series and exercised some problems on the theorem under partition method. This new idea can enable the scientific researchers for research and development further.

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